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THE ROLE OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A MODERN SPECIALIST

Akramova Dilnoza Numanjonovna

*Lecturer of the Department of Applied Foreign Languages,
Andijan State Pedagogical Institute*

Abstract: The use of English in professional settings is an integral part of modern global business and communication. As one of the most widely spoken foreign languages, English is widely used in various professional fields, including media, information technology, finance, medicine, and education. Analyzing English use in these fields allows us to understand the specific language practices that influence professional success and effective interaction in an international environment.

Keywords: means of communication, professional competences, professional mobility, occupation-oriented foreign language communication, non-linguistic students, English in pedagogy.

Introduction

Every year, more and more people are learning English for career success and advancement. It's important to understand that English proficiency requirements vary depending on the chosen profession: journalists need fluency for interviews and reporting, while programmers need it to read documentation and communicate with colleagues from other countries.

Methods

The following authors have paid attention to the problem of teaching foreign languages to students majoring in non-linguistic specialties: N.D. Galskova, T.Yu. Zagryazkina, G.A. Kitaygorodskaya, O.E. Lomakina, R.P. Milrud, O.G. Polyakov, T. Hutchinson, A. Waters, and others. The problem remains relevant today: the level of foreign language proficiency among students majoring in non-linguistic specialties does not always meet the requirements of modern society.

Results and analysis

English plays a significant role in pedagogy, serving as a key tool for learning and communication in the modern world. In education, English is used both as a means of communication between teachers and students and for studying specialized materials and literature in a foreign language.

In the modern world, education is considered to be the main factor ensuring the stable development of civilization and humanity as a whole. The intellectual, cultural and spiritual potential of society is formed in the education system. Particular attention to the modern education system is due to the fact that education as a result is the basis for solving the socio-economic problems of society, preserving and developing science and culture, industry and technology. At the current stage of society's development, there is a general trend of interaction between cultures, integration of state education into the global space, as well as expansion of ties in various fields of activity, including professional. As a result, in recent decades, throughout the world and in Uzbekistan, requirements for the results of general and especially higher professional education, for a number of reasons, have been formulated exclusively in the category of competence. The attention of domestic specialists began to be attracted by American, and then European publications on the problems of personnel training. Publications devoted to the analysis of various foreign educational models aroused great interest. The leading factors in updating the development of competencies include academic mobility and the globalization of education; expansion of the field of professional activity, professional communication with representatives of other cultures, various social groups [2]. All this requires a rethinking of the

process of training specialists in the process of vocational education and the formation of professional competence. The concept of professional competence is not generally accepted and unambiguously defined. In most sources, professional competence is an integral quality of a specialist, characterizing the ability to solve professional problems using professional knowledge, existing experience and formed attitude to professional activity, readiness for self-education in a professional environment [6]. Along with these trends, the process of training a modern specialist in Uzbekistan is undergoing significant changes. Modern society needs educated specialists capable of making independent decisions in situations of choice, ready for cooperation, distinguished by mobility and responsibility. In the context of increasing professional and academic exchanges, international cooperation, a foreign language is becoming one of the leading resources for the development of society at the present stage. Knowledge of a foreign language, and often several, is becoming an indispensable indicator of education. In this regard, society places certain demands on a modern specialist, including not only the possession of foreign language communication skills at the everyday level, but also a certain level of proficiency in a foreign language for professional communication (study of professional activity using the example of foreign experience, establishing contacts at a general professional level, ensuring readiness to work in a foreign language environment) [6].

Teachers working in the field of pedagogy must have a good level of English to successfully perform their professional duties. They use English to conduct lessons, explain new material, assign homework, and assess student progress. Teachers also frequently use English to communicate with colleagues at international conferences and seminars, share experiences, and participate in professional networks.

Using English in pedagogy also expands teachers' access to the latest educational technologies, teaching methods, and research in pedagogy. Modern teachers actively use online resources, multimedia materials, webinars, and courses in English to enhance their skills and professional development.

Using English in pedagogy also promotes intercultural understanding and enriches teachers' professional experience. Interacting with teachers and education specialists from around the world helps expand horizons, learn about best practices and approaches to teaching, and share experiences in methodology and pedagogical practice.

UNESCO has declared the 21st century the century of polyglots, with the motto "Learning languages throughout life." Most foreigners speak several languages. Unfortunately, our compatriots are reluctant to learn foreign languages. Many of us underestimate the importance of mastering at least one foreign language. One way to increase the competitiveness of specialists in today's labor market is to learn and continually improve their foreign language skills. Today's university graduates often face difficulties finding a job, as employers are interested not only in the skills, experience, and length of service of a potential employee, but also in their foreign language proficiency. Language proficiency is not so much an indicator of a person's level of education as it is of their potential for success within the company. A graduate who speaks a foreign language has a better chance of getting a job, becoming a highly paid employee, and subsequently, successfully advancing in their career. It is desirable for applicants to be proficient not only in everyday language but also in professional terms, i.e., to be proficient in the language for specific purposes. Typically, applicants for a position at a prestigious company undergo several interviews and are also asked to prepare an application package in English (a resume, recommendation, cover letter, and a letter requesting additional information), prepare a project, and solve a case in a foreign language. Thus, in her article "Language Education as a Component of Individual Economic Capital in the Modern Labor Market," E.A. Mikhaleva rightly notes that knowledge of languages is one of the important requirements for managers at any level [7]. Thus, a foreign language is both a tool for survival in new conditions and a component of professional success. Knowledge of a foreign language is no longer simply a valuable asset; it is an urgent necessity. Of course, mastering a foreign language is possible through various courses, which are so popular today. However, this requires additional time and money, and the employer requires a specialist "here and now" who speaks at least one foreign language and, as noted above, at a professional level. Higher

education institutions are called upon to address this challenge. In this regard, the role of the “Foreign Language” discipline in professional training is significantly increasing. The goal of foreign language teaching at a university is no longer so much to develop intercultural communication skills, but rather to develop the ability to professionally communicate in a multicultural environment.

Conclusion

Thus, the integration of education in Uzbekistan into the global educational space requires increasing the competitiveness of modern specialists in the labor market, whose primary quality is professional foreign language competence. In this regard, the role of the foreign languages in professional spheres is significantly increasing, as classes develop foreign language communication skills in specific professional, business, and scientific situations. In conclusion, it should be noted that the foreign language in professional spheres is essential and mandatory for study at a modern university, regardless of the chosen profession, as proficiency in a foreign language offers enormous opportunities in communication, education, and career.

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